

Overcoming borders: Spina bifida and European Cooperation

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Abstract

Spina bifida aperta is one of the most serious malformations in humans. Worldwide, the abortion rate is estimated at 63%. In recent decades, significant progress has been made in prevention, diagnosis and treatment. The long-term outcome for children with Spina bifida aperta is significantly dependent on the level of the lesion and the timing of surgical treatment. It has been clearly shown that prepartum closure of the lesion reduces loss of function in motor skills and sensitivity. The case report about a Georgian child with prenatally diagnosed spina bifida aperta is intended to show that highly specialized medicine is also available to affected families beyond national borders. The Georgian woman underwent a Fetoscopic Patch Closure. Good postpartum follow-up care and special physiotherapeutic treatment of the children increase and ensure the success of the operation. Collaborations within Europe for the medical care of Spina bifida aperta should be formed and made easier accessible to parents. The quality of medical care in all European countries can benefit from collegial cooperation. Overcoming borders instead of building borders can be life-decisive in individual cases. It needs courage to take the step forward and professional moderation between the players. Not all European countries are able to provide appropriate prenatal surgical care. This intra-European cooperation could only succeed because there were convinced and committed players and shows that speciality medicine can also succeed beyond European borders. We need international efforts and funding to be able to offer affected families an alternative to abortion.

1. Background

Spina bifida is a congenital disease with various clinical signs. It is assumed that spina bifida occurs in 3.4 per 100,000 newborns (Atta, 2016). In 2023, the number of newborns in Georgia was 40,214, which means that the rate of incidence of this malformation in this small European country is 1.36. Worldwide, the abortion rate is estimated at 63% (Trudell & Odibo, 2014). Symptoms generally include weakness of the back muscles, limited mobility and urological problems. The level of the lesion typically determines the severity of the symptoms. The cause is abnormal development of the neural tube, which can also cause a Chiari type 2 malformation with hypoplasia of the cerebellum and herniation of the lower part of the brain into the spinal canal. Obstructive hydrocephalus is a common complication in the course of the disease. Typically, spina bifida can be reliably diagnosed in early pregnancy using 2D or 3D sonography. The diagnosis should be confirmed by amniocentesis and further genetic defects should be ruled out. Children diagnosed with spina bifida benefit noticeably and sustainably if it is closed in utero rather than postpartum (Adzick, et al., 2011) (Brun, et al., 2023). A study on long-term outcome published in 2021 showed that more than twice as many children treated in utero were able to walk without aids at school age (Meuli & Möhrlein, 2021). The children who underwent early surgery were not only faster, their gait quality itself was better and more stable and the risk of excessive lordosis was also lower. In addition, they were only half as likely to have more extensive functional impairment than would be expected based on the anatomical level of the lesion on the spinal cord. All this means that the children can lead a self-determined life. Foetal surgery not only has advantages for the preservation of motor skills, but also for the mental development of the children. This is partly due to the fact that foetal surgery can also significantly reduce shunt rate (Tamber, Flannery, Mc Clung-Smith, & al, 2019). Most children would develop hydrocephalus without a shunt, and those operated on intrauterine are less likely to require a shunt.

2. Case presentation

A 42-year-old Georgian woman becomes pregnant spontaneously after 10 years of secondary infertility. No known previous illnesses or malformations in the family history. The foetus was sonographically diagnosed with spina bifida as early as 13 weeks' gestation. and the foetus develops lemon and banana signs, which were first described in the 17th week of pregnancy (Figure 1). The spina bifida aperta lumbalis (26mm) could already be precisely classified as such. The local doctors recommended the termination of the pregnancy, as neither prenatal nor postnatal care is guaranteed in Georgia. The parents were not satisfied with this and looked for alternative solutions. A German gynaecologist put them in touch with the DZFT - German Centre for Foetal Surgery and Minimally Invasive Therapy at Mannheim University Hospital.

male baby was born with good APGAR and pH values. For the first 4 weeks of life, the boy was cared for in the NICU of the neonatology clinic and looked after by specialists in neurosurgery at the University Medical Centre Mannheim (UMM) until the patch was completely covered by secondary skin (Figure 2).

Figure 2: Findings of Patch closure after birth and after 1 month

2.2. Follow-up in the first year of life

The parents had regular sonography checks of the child's head. In addition, the head circumference was measured monthly by the parents. Mild ventriculomegaly developed in the 4th month of life. The cerebral ventricles were measured sonographically every month and reached a plateau at the age of 9 months (Figure 4). The 3rd ventricle was 7.7 mm (Figure 6) and thus three times larger. The two lateral ventricles were enlarged eightfold at 35 mm on the left and 32 mm on the right (norm 4 mm) (Figure 5). As the child showed no signs of intracranial pressure such as tiredness, somnolence, dizziness or vomiting and the head circumference did not exceed the 97th percentile in growth (Figure 3), a CSF shunt insertion was not performed. The motor development of the lower extremities is delayed and cannot be conclusively assessed at the moment, nor can the achievement of urinary incontinence be estimated due to the infant's age. Other early childhood development was normal.

Figure 3: Development of head circumference compared with percentiles (Schienkiewitz, Schaffrath-Rosario, Dortschy, Ellert, & H., 2011)

Figure 4: Neurosonography at the age of 5 and 12 months

Figure 5: Measurements of cerebral lateral ventricles

Figure 6: Measurements of the 3rd ventricle of the brain

2.3. Hydro-Rehabilitation

Vera Kereselidze, co-founder of the Federation of Infant Swimming in Georgia, was the first to adapt the hydro-rehabilitation method to a child with spina bifida. This physiotherapeutic method aims to promote physical, emotional and cognitive development through movement in water. The therapy for the boy was started before he reached the age of 6 months. Children at this age are not yet able to perform tasks consciously, so natural reflexes and self-preservation instincts were used to help the child perform necessary movements. This approach helped to

gradually develop coordination, strengthen muscles and develop basic movement skills without overtaxing the child. In the first few days of training, the physiotherapy team focussed on strengthening the neck muscles. This was followed by deep dives whose complexity was gradually increased. Initially, the dives took place in the first and second layer of water. At the end of the first month, they moved on to the third layer. The aim of these exercises was to centralise blood circulation in order to maximise oxygen supply to the brain and stimulate the formation of neuronal connections. After the first results were achieved, work began on strengthening the back and side muscles, which provide stability and prepare the child's body for further strain. After six months, work began on developing and strengthening the leg muscles. Compared to children whose spina bifida was only treated after birth, a significant difference in the effectiveness of rehabilitation can be observed. In cases where spina bifida was treated surgically after birth, it is more difficult to achieve such a rehabilitative result. In addition, children with this diagnosis often do not have the opportunity to exercise regularly and systematically, which significantly impairs the rehabilitation process. This example shows how important regularity and consistency in training are. Thanks to constant practice and an individualised approach, remarkable results were achieved, which is unfortunately not always possible for children with more complex conditions and irregular exercise (Kereselidze, 20.11.2024).

3. Discussion

The quality of medical care in all European countries can benefit from collegial co-operation. Overcoming borders instead of building borders can be life-decisive in individual cases, as the example shows. It takes courage to take the step forward. A professional moderation between the players is indispensable. Follow-up care for the affected child does not end when they are discharged from the maternity clinic, but must continue for years in close dialogue with the parents. This case was the first time that the Georgian colleagues learnt about the possibility of percutaneous minimally invasive Fetoscopic Patch Surgery. The physiotherapeutic treatment was successful because a dedicated team set out to find a solution. Easy-to-understand instructions for the parents in the follow-up, in particular the documentation of findings and progress and their preparation for the rapid assessment of the specialists involved, proved to be essential. Parents need encouragement and support in order to be able to deal with their fears.

4. Conclusion

This European cooperation could only succeed because there were convinced and committed players and shows that speciality medicine can also succeed beyond European borders. The financing of these individual cases should be included in foreign policy negotiations. Countries that are unable to establish their own speciality centres due to their geographical size should be given the opportunity to use the existing potential within Europe. In our case, the Georgian state has contributed to the best of its ability, even if the associated costs could not be fully covered. Financing funds need to be set up at international level.

5. Declaration

Ethics approval:	Not applicable
Consent for publication:	Written informed consent was obtained from the patient for publication of this case report and any accompanying images. A copy of the written consent is available for review by the Editor-in-Chief of this journal
Competing interests:	There are no financial and non-financial interests to declare.
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Consent to participate:	All information collected will remain confidential and will be stored securely. Only aggregate results will be reported. Data available upon request
Authors' contributions:	The authors read and approved the final manuscript.

List of Abbreviation

DZFT	Fetal Surgery & Minimally Invasive Therapy
CSF	Cerebrospinal Fluid
SpA	Spinal Anaesthesia
SBA	Spina bifida aperta

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References

- Adzick, N. S., Thom, E. A., Spong, C. Y., Brock III, J. W., Burrows, P. K., Johnson, M. P., & al, e. (2011). A randomized trial of prenatal versus postnatal repair of myelomeningocele. *New England Journal of Medicine*, *11*(364), S. 993-1004. doi:10.1056/NEJMoa11014379
- Atta, C. A. (2016). Global Birth Prevalence of Spina Bifida by Folic Acid Fortification Status: A Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis. *Am J Public Health*, p. 106. doi:10.2105/AJPH.2015.302902
- Brun, B., Wille, D., Schauer, S., Moehrlen, U., Meuli, M., Latel, B., & Padden, B. (2023). Motor function outcomes in children with open prenatal repair of Spina bifida aperta at 36-month follow-up: The Zurich cohort. (16), pp. 595-604. doi:10.3233/PRM-220096
- Diehl, D., Belke, F., Kohl, T., Axt-Fliedner, R., Degenhardt, J., Khaleeva, A., . . . Neubauer, B. (2021). Fully percutaneous fetoscopic repair of myelomeningocele: 30 month follow-up data. (57), pp. 113-118. doi:10.1002/uog.22116
- Kereselidze, V. (20.11.2024). *Therapy Report*. Federation of Infant Swimming in Georgia, Physiotherapy, Tblissi.
- Kohl, T. (2014). Percutaneous minimally invasive fetoscopic surgery for spina bifida aperta. Part I: surgical technique and perioperative outcome. (44), pp. 515-524. doi:10.1002/uog.13430
- Kohl, T. (2024). Spina bifida aperta. *Neonatologie Scan*(13), pp. 51-71. doi:10.1055/a-1817-2248
- Meuli, M., & Möhrlen, U. (2021). Long-term Outcomes of Children After Fetal Surgery for Spina bifida - Torward Sustainability. p. 175. doi:10.1001/jamapediatrics.2020.5687
- Schienkiewitz, A., Schaffrath-Rosario, Dortschy, R., Ellert, U., & H., N. (2011). German head circumference references for infants, children and adolescents in comparison with currently used national and international references. *Acta Paediatrica*, *100*(7), pp. e298-e33. doi:10.1111/j.1651-2227.2011.02173.x
- Tamber, M., Flannery, A., Mc Clung-Smith, C., & al, e. (2019). Systematic Review and Evidence-Based Guideline on the Incidence of Shunt-Dependent Hydrocephalus in Infants with Myelomeningocele after prenatal versus postnatal Repair. *Neurosurgery*, p. 85.
- Trudell, A., & Odibo, A. (2014). Diagnosis of spina bifida on ultrasound: Always termination? (E. Ltd., Ed.) *Best Prac Res Clin Obstet Gynaecol*, *28*(3), pp. 367-377. doi:10.1016/j.bpobgyn.2013.10.006